

Anti-arthritic activity of *Cleome gynandra*; an *in vitro* and *in silico* analysis

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Abstract

Arthritis, a major problem these days, demands a safer alternative without side effects and low toxicity, as the currently available medicines lead to long-term problems. Thus, this study aims to identify the anti-arthritic activity of an herbal plant, *Cleome gynandra* (CG), through *in vitro* and *in silico* studies. The Soxhlet extract of CG leaves was yielded and subjected to qualitative, quantitative and gas chromatography mass spectroscopy (GCMS) analysis. Based on the GCMS results, the compounds were selected and docked against the important arthritis-causing proteins, signal transducer and activator of transcription 1- alpha/beta (STAT 1) and hexameric human IL-6/IL-6 alpha receptor. Further, the cytotoxicity, anti-inflammatory and wound healing assays were performed to estimate the anti-arthritic activities. The results revealed that CG contains potential phytochemicals such as alkaloids (1.25 g) and terpenoids (2 g). GCMS results revealed the presence of Phenol, 2,4-bis (1,1-dimethylethyl), phosphite (3:1) and 1,4-benzenedicarboxylic acid, bis (2-ethylhexyl) ester with the highest peak areas of 39.09 % and 13.77 %, respectively. Hence, these compounds, Phenol, 2,4-bis (1,1-dimethylethyl), phosphite (3:1) and 1,4-benzenedicarboxylic acid, bis (2-ethylhexyl) ester, were docked against the STAT1 and IL-6 proteins, respectively. They exhibited the binding affinities of -4.7 kcal/mole and -5.3 kcal/mole, respectively. Further, the cytotoxic activity by MTT assay, in MG-63 cell lines, was found to be 483.1 µg/mL (IC₅₀). This indicates increased cell viability, representing low toxicity to the cell lines. The ELISA anti-inflammatory assay showed reduced IL-6 in CG-treated (67.62 pg/mL) compared to LPS-mediated samples (74.65 pg/mL). CG treatment reduced the wound area and promoted cell migration at a concentration of 130.28 µg/mL in 3T3-L1 fibroblast cells. Thereby,

the study concludes that the CG extract contains effective phytochemicals and exhibits potential anti-arthritic activity. Thus, this study recommends the use of CG and its components as a proficient source for arthritis treatments.

Keywords:

Anti-arthritis, *Cleome gynandra*, phytochemicals, docking, anti-inflammatory, cytotoxicity and wound-healing.

1. Introduction

Arthritis is a joint-related disease that causes inflammation, stiffness, pain, and swelling of the joint muscles (Elgaddal et al., 2024). It commonly occurs in the joints that bear weight, such as the hip, knee and spine. Though it is generally considered to occur among the old aged people due to natural aging, sometimes people of a younger age are also found affected by injury (Foran RH Jared, 2021). Arthritis increased up to 53.9% in older age people over 75 years, whereas only 3.6% were affected between the ages of 18 and 34. Moreover, women are prone to arthritis compared to men, as only 16.1% of men were affected, whereas 21.5% of women were affected, according to the National Health Interview Survey (NHIS) as per the 2022 report (Elgaddal et al., 2024). Specifically, among Indians, a minimal 20% of the population possesses any one of the arthritic conditions (Goel & Kulshrestha, 2021). The World Health Organization (WHO) reported that all over the world, approximately 18 million people are suffering from arthritis, among whom 75% are women and 55% are elderly (Rheumatoid Arthritis, 2023).

Types of arthritis may outnumber 100 conditions (Fallon et al., 2023) however, mainly it includes four types as osteoarthritis, inflammatory arthritis, post-traumatic arthritis and Septic arthritis (Foran RH Jared, 2021). Osteoarthritis, post-traumatic arthritis and septic arthritis are caused due to the overuse, injury and infection of the joints, respectively. Contradictorily, inflammatory arthritis includes different types such as rheumatoid arthritis, psoriatic arthritis, crystalline arthropathy, lyme arthritis, spondylic arthritis, lupus arthritis and juvenile arthritis (Senthelal et al., 2025). The causes of these types vary, as rheumatoid arthritis is an autoimmune disease, and psoriatic arthritis is due to psoriasis. Crystalline arthropathy is of two types as gout and pseudogout, based on the buildup of uric acid or calcium pyrophosphate in the bloodstream, respectively. Lyme arthritis is caused by Lyme disease, spondylytic arthritis affects the spine, lupus arthritis is a type of autoimmune disease, and juvenile arthritis affects children (Foran RH

Jared, 2021). If left untreated, it may lead to severe pain and difficulty leading a normal life. This, in turn, may cause anxiety, depression and hinder social life (Theis KA et al., 2021). Though there are multiple non-steroidal and steroidal drugs, there is no total cure for the disease. The discomfort and pain can be managed only through treatment methods and medications (Goel & Kulshrestha, 2021) (Foran RH Jared, 2021).

The major pro-inflammatory cytokines that degrade the cartilage tissues, leading to inflammation, include tumor necrosis factor (TNF α), Interleukin 6 (IL-6), and Interleukin 1 β (Goel & Kulshrestha, 2021). The conventionally used drugs, such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medicines (NSAIDs), corticosteroids, paracetamol, ibuprofen, disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs), IL – inhibitors, are swapped by some biologicals like IL-antagonists, JANUS kinase inhibitors and TNF monoclonal antibodies (Chandana G et al., 2022) (Ali et al., 2023) (Kukreti et al., 2022) (Goel & Kulshrestha, 2021) (Ben Mrid et al., 2022). These drugs, on prolonged usage, lead to side effects such as myocardial infarction, hepatotoxicity, gastrointestinal toxicity, bleeding and ulceration (Kukreti et al., 2022). Hence, alternatives that can be used long-term without any side effects need to be identified.

Herbal medicines, known for their nil toxicity, have made a comeback among recent researchers to look for effective and long-term arthritis treatments (Sharma et al., 2023). Nearly 80% of the population depends on herbal medicines even today, according to the WHO report (WHO Establishes the Global Centre for Traditional Medicine in India, 2022). Thus, there is a need to explore the phytochemicals present in the plants and utilize them effectively (Deligiannidou et al., 2021). On such an approach, plant materials such as *Phoenix dactylifera*, *Punica granatum*, *Ribes orientale*, *Circaea mollis*, *Clematis orientalis*, *Schefflera octophylla*, *Ephedra gerardiana*, *Camellia sinensis*, *Bawei Longzuan*, etc have been widely studied against arthritis (Deligiannidou et al., 2021). All these studies have analysed the efficacy of the plants in anti-arthritis activity through assays. The studies reported the reduction of TNF α , predominant proinflammatory cytokine, reduction of swelling, and antioxidant activity. However, the specific interactions between the phytochemicals present and the inflammation-causing proteins remain unexplored.

Cleome is a common weed, with over 200 species that grow in almost all tropical countries. The genus is historically known for its potential in various treatments (Roy et al., 2024) (Narendhirakannan et al., 2007). Among which, each part of *Cleome gynandra* (CG), such as leaves and seeds, that favour head and stomach aches, sap in epileptic fits or ear aches, and decoction of leaves in easing childbirth have been reported. More specifically, the bruised leaves have been identified to treat localized pains and rheumatism (Narendhirakannan et al., 2007). Phytoconstituents are known to reduce fever, inflammation, and relieve pain (Khuntia et al., 2022) (Naeem et al., 2023). Rosdi et al., (2024) confirmed the effective anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antifungal, and anti-arthritic activities of *C. gynandra* (Mohamad Rosdi et al., 2025). It is also considered to be a safe alternative for non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (Lakshmi S. Pillai & Bindu R. Nair, 2014). Considering this, the current study aimed to identify the efficacy of CG in antiarthritic activity. Moreover, a particular study that specifically analyses the compounds present in a plant, its binding affinity towards the target protein, anti-cytotoxicity, anti-inflammatory and wound healing capacity remains unexplored. Thus, this study focuses on detecting the predominant phytochemical present in CG and identifying its potential to inhibit the target proteins responsible for arthritic activity. Additionally, it also estimates its *in vitro* anti-arthritic property.

2. Materials

The cell lines; MG-63 (Human osteosarcoma cells) and 3T3-L1 (Murine Fibroblast cells) were purchased from National Centre for Cellular Sciences (NCCS), Pune. Gas chromatography - Mass spectroscopy (GCMS) model used was GCMS-QP2010SE. ELISA was purchased from Invitrogen, USA. All the chemicals were purchased from Invitrogen, USA and Sigma, India.

3. Methodology

3.1 Plant material extraction and analysis

3.1.1 Plant collection and extraction

Cleome gynandra (CG) was collected from nearby area of Thingalur, Erode District. The collected plant was authenticated and certified by a taxonomist at Botanical Survey of India (BSI), Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, (Plant Identification No. BSI/SRC/5/23/2022/Tech/649).. The collected plant was de-leaved, washed and dried in the shade. The dried leaves were crushed using a mortar and pestle to obtain a fine powder to increase the

surface area of the compounds. The powdered leaf of 500 g was subjected to Soxhlet extraction with hydroalcoholic solvent of 900 mL, at 40-50 °C for 4 hours (Kumar et al., 2021) (Das et al., 2025). The obtained hydroalcoholic extract was stored at 4 °C in an airtight container for future use (Khalid et al., 2021).

3.1.2 Phytochemicals analysis

The qualitative analysis of the phytochemicals was performed as per the standard procedures (Kumar et al., 2021). The tests included qualitative analysis of Carboxylic acid, Tannins, Steroids, Flavanoids, Glycosides, Proteins, Phenol, Alkaloids, Gum, flavanoglycoside, Carbohydrates and resins (Farooq et al., 2022).

3.1.3 Quantification of phytochemicals

3.1.3.1 Alkaloids

CG sample (1.25 g) was dissolved in 200 mL of 10% acetic acid in ethanol. The solution was left undisturbed for 4 hours and heated to one-quarter of its original volume and filtered. To it, 15 drops of ammonium hydroxide (NH₄OH) was added and incubated at room temperature for 3 hours. After incubation, the supernatant was discarded, and the precipitate was washed with 20 mL of 0.1M NH₄OH and filtered again. The filtered precipitate was weighed to quantify the amount of alkaloid present in the sample.

3.1.3.2 Flavonoids

Aluminium chloride colorimetric assay was performed. Two test tubes, one containing 1 ml of CG sample and the other with 1 ml of standard quercetin solution (50 mg/ml) were taken. Then, 4 ml of distilled water and 0.3 ml of 5 % sodium nitrite solution were added to both the tubes and incubated for 5 minutes. After incubation, 2 mL of 1 M sodium hydroxide was added and made up to 10 mL with distilled water and mixed well. The development of orange yellowish colour was observed and spectrophotometric absorbance was measured at 510 nm using UV-visible instrument. The experiment was performed in triplicate using distilled water as the blank. A graph was plotted using quercetin as standard, and the amount of flavonoids were expressed as mg of quercetin equivalents/ 100 g of dry mass.

3.1.3.3 Total Phenol content

Total phenolic content was estimated by Folin Ciocalteu's method. Two test tubes, one containing 1 ml of CG sample and the other with 1 ml of standard gallic acid (0.007 mg/ml to 1mg/ml) were taken in triplicate. To it, 5 ml of distilled water and 0.5 ml of Folin Ciocalteu's reagent were added and mixed well. After 5 minutes of incubation, 1.5 ml of 20 % sodium carbonate was added and its volume was made up to 10 ml with distilled water. The tubes were incubated for 2 hours. After observation of blue colour spectrophotometric absorbance was measured at 750 nm using a UV-visible instrument. The reagent blank with solvent was used as blank, where gallic acid was used as standard, to plot the calibration curve. The amount of phenolic content in the sample was expressed as mg of gallic acid equivalent weight / 100 g of dry mass.

3.1.3.4 Terpenoids

The powdered leaves (1g) were soaked in ethanol for 24 hours. After incubation, the samples were filtered and extracted using petroleum ether. The solution was dried and the remaining powder were weighed to measure the amount of terpenoids present in the sample.

3.1.3.5 Total ash

CG sample (1 g) was placed in an incineration dish and heated for 30 minutes at 550°C using a muffle furnace. After cooling, the sample was weighed to the nearest of 0.001 g.

3.1.3.6 Protein estimation using Bradford's Method

Bovine serum albumin (BSA) standard was prepared and 10µl was added to a tube. Simultaneously, the sample was also added in another tube. To the BSA and sample solutions, 100 µl of Bradford's reagent was added and incubated for 10 minutes. After blue colour change, the spectrometric readings were taken at 595 nm, and the calibration curve was plotted.

3.1.3.7 Estimation of reducing sugar using Benedict's Method

Sugar was estimated using glucose solution as a standard. 10 µL of standard and sample were added to the test tubes in triplicate. Further, 200 µl of benedict's reagent was added to the tubes and heated for 10 minutes. The absorbance was then measured at 595 nm.

3.1.3.8 Lipid estimation by Vanillin method

Two tubes, one with standard solution containing 0.05 g of cholesterol in 1 ml of chloroform: methanol (2:1) solution, and the other containing 100 µl of sample was taken. 100 µl of concentrated sulfuric acid was added to the tubes, and incubated for 10 minutes at 90°C, using a water bath. After cooling, 100 µl of vanillin solution was added, and the absorbance was measured at 540 nm.

3.1.4 GCMS analysis

The hydroalcoholic extract of CG leaves were analyzed for their GCMS profile. The Shimadzu Gas Chromatograph was coupled mass detector (GCMS-QP2010SE). 1 ml of the sample was injected in the split mode (1:10), where the instrument's specification included; capillary columns - 30 m, 250 µm, oven temperature - 250°C, Injection port temperature - 280°C, Helium flow rate - 1 ml/min, ionization voltage - 70 eV, mass Spectral scans range - 40-450 (MHz), Transfer line - 200°C and source temperature - 350°C.

3.2 Molecular docking

3.2.1 Preparation of ligand

The 3D structures (SDF format) of the phytochemicals (ligands) were downloaded from the PubChem website. The structures were visualized and converted to PDB format using BIOVIA Discovery Studio software. The PDB formats of the ligands were converted to PDBQT format using Auto Dock 4.2.6 software.

3.2.2 Preparation of target protein

The target proteins were downloaded from the RCSB Protein Data Bank database in PDB format. BIOVIA Discovery Studio software was used to visualize and optimize the target proteins. Optimization was carried out by deleting the heteroatoms and water molecules. Further, the polar hydrogens and active site were determined. The, AutoDock 4.2.6 software was used to convert the format of protein structure from PDB to PDBQT. The obtained target protein was subjected to molecular docking.

3.2.3 Docking of ligands with target protein

To perform molecular docking, conf. file was prepared and docked using AutoDock vina software. Based on the GCMS results, two pair of ligands and proteins were selected for docking. First set included the docking of phenol, 2,4 -bis (1,1 - dimethylethyl)-, phosphite (3:1) (PubChem

CID: 91601) with Signal transducer and activator of transcription 1- alpha/beta (PDB id: 1YVL) (STAT1). Second set included 1, 4-Benzenedicarboxylic Acid/ Bis (2-Ethyl Hexyl) Ester against the crystal structure of Hexameric Human IL-6/IL-6 Alpha Receptor. The 3D structures of the ligands, target proteins and their optimized structures are shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: 3D structures of the ligands, target proteins and their optimized structures.

Image description: A – Ligand of first set (phenol, 2,4 –bis (1,1 – dimethylethyl)-, phosphite (3:1) (PubChem CID: 91601); B - Target protein of first set (Signal transducer and activator of transcription 1- alpha/beta (PDB id: 1YVL); C – Optimized structure of first set’s target protein; D – Ligand of second set (1, 4-Benzenedicarboxylic Acid/ Bis (2-Ethyl Hexyl) Ester); E - Target protein of second set (Hexameric Human IL-6/IL-6 Alpha Receptor); F - Optimized structure of second set’s target protein.

3.3 Cell culture studies

3.4 Cell line culturing

The cell lines (MG-63 and 3T3-L1 cells) were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), where the liquid medium was supplemented with 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), 100 µg/ml penicillin, and 100 µg/ml streptomycin. The cultured medium was maintained at 37°C under atmospheric conditions of 5% CO₂ for further use. All the procedures were carried out using purified distilled water.

3.4.1 Cytotoxicity study by MTT assay

MG-63 cell lines were pooled in a 15 ml tube and added to the 96-well tissue culture plate at a density of 1×10^5 cells/ml/well (200 µL). Then, the cells were washed with Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and treated with the test sample (CG) in triplicate, and incubated at 37°C under atmospheric conditions of 5% CO₂ for 24 hours. After incubation, 10 µL of MTT (5 mg/ml) was added to each well and incubated for another 2 to 4 hours, until purple precipitates were visualized under an inverted microscope. Finally, the total components in the well containing medium, test samples and MTT (220 µL), were washed with 200 µl of 1X PBS. In addition, to dissolve the formazan crystals formed, 100 µL of DMSO was added to the wells and shaken for 5 minutes. The absorbance of the samples was estimated using a microplate reader (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), at 570 nm. Further, GraphPad Prism 6.0 software (USA) was used to calculate the percentage of cell viability and IC₅₀. The formula used was as follows;

$$\text{Formula Cell viability\%} = \text{Test OD/Control OD} \times 100$$

Simultaneously, another set of cells, after incubation, were stained using acridine orange and ethidium bromide (10 µl of 1 mg/ml). After staining, the plates were centrifuged at 800 rpm for 2 minutes and visualized immediately. At least 100 cells were viewed using a fluorescence cell imaging system with a fluorescent filter.

3.4.2 Anti-inflammatory activity by albumin denaturation assay

Anti-inflammatory activity of the test sample (CG) at varying concentrations of 500, 250, 100, 50 and 10 µg/mL was estimated by calculating its ability to inhibit protein denaturation. Acetyl salicylic acid was used for positive control. All the tests were carried out in triplicate. For test samples, 500 µl of 1% bovine serum albumin was added to the test samples (CG) of different concentrations and incubated at ambient temperature for 10 minutes. Further, the samples were

heated at 51°C for 20 minutes. After cooling the sample solution, OD values were observed at 660 nm. Inhibition % of protein denaturation was calculated using the formula;

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of protein denaturation} = 100 - ((A1-A2)/A0) * 100$$

Where, A1 = Absorbance of control, A2 = Absorbance of test samples, A0 = Absorbance of positive control.

IC50 value was used to plot the dose response curve. Inhibition of inflammatory cytokines, interleukin 6 (IL-6) was quantified using sandwich ELISA and the reaction was measured using a microtiter plate at 450 nm.

3.4.3. Wound healing assay

3T3-L1 cells were seeded into the six-well tissue culture dish and grown up to 90% confluency in complete medium. With a plastic tip of 1 mm, the cell monolayer was wounded and washed with medium (four times) to remove the cell debris. Cells were further incubated in 1 % Fetal bovine serum (FBS) medium for 48 hours and used as a control. Test samples were treated with 130.28 µg/ml of CG and incubated for 24 hours. After incubation, the cells were monitored using an inverted microscope, mounted with a camera, and the wound area was measured using Image-J software (NIH, Bethesda, MD, USA). The wound area percentage was calculated by comparing the wound area of the control and the treated samples.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Plant extraction and phytochemical analysis

The crude extract of *Cleome* is already known for its therapeutic properties. But recently, their phytochemical constituents have gained importance due to their pharmacological benefits, especially in the field of drug design (Singh et al., 2018). Thus, this study performed Soxhlet extraction of the plant leaves and quantified the phytochemicals present in it. The extract yielded was % or g/ml of CG sample. In the same way, Narendhirakannan et al., (2007) also extracted 3.2g/100g from CG using the Soxhlet method (Narendhirakannan et al., 2007). Qualitative analysis of the phytochemicals confirmed the presence of resins, carbohydrates, alkaloids, terpenoids, total ash and proteins. Carbohydrates, protein, alkaloids, terpenoids, and total ash were quantified to be

0.04 mg/ml, 0.977 mg/mL, 1.25 g, 2 g, and 0.81%, respectively. All other components were absent in the CG extract. The results showing the qualitative analysis and quantification of tested phytochemicals are tabulated in **Table 1**. More than 37 phytoconstituents were found in *C. viscosa* such as alkaloids, quinones, coumarins, terpenoids and flavonoids. On comparing *C. viscosa* and *C. burmanni*, *C. viscosa* showed increased phenolic content than *C. burmanni* (Lakshmi S. Pillai & Bindu R. Nair, 2014). Each part of the plants of *Cleome* consists of different phytochemicals, and almost all of them can be used as therapeutic compounds (Singh et al., 2018).

Table 1: Qualitative and quantitative analysis of phytochemicals present in CG sample

S. No.	Phytochemical compound	Qualitative result	Quantification
1.	Resins	+	
2.	Carboxylic acid	-	
3.	Tanins	-	
4.	Steroids	-	
5.	Flavonoid	-	
6.	Carbohydrates	+	0.04 mg/ml
7.	Glycosides	-	
8.	Saponification	-	
9.	Protein	+	0.977 mg/mL
10.	Phenol	-	
11.	Biuret	-	
12.	Soponin	-	
13.	Gum	-	
14.	Flavanoglycosides	-	
15.	Alkaloids	+	1.25 g
16.	Terpenoids	+	2 g
17.	Total ash	+	0.81%

Note: “-” indicates absence of the compound

4.2 GCMS

For over 40 years, the secondary metabolites present in the different species of *Cleome* have been studied. The major groups included coumarinolignoids, dipyrrodiadiazepinone, dollabellane diterpene, cembranoid diterpene, bicyclic diterpene, diterpene alcohol, trinortriterpenoid and pentacyclic triterpenoid (Singh et al., 2018). Likewise, the GCMS analysis (**Figure 2**) of CG sample showed the presence of many compounds, however, a few were determined with increased peak area. The compounds with increased peak area include 1,4-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, bis(2-ethylhexyl) ester, Phenol, 2,4-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-, phosphite (3:1), Phthalic acid, cyclobutyl tridecyl ester, 4,13-dibenzoyl [2.2] paracyclophane and 1,1,2-triphenylpropene. Among these, Phenol, 2,4-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-, phosphite (3:1) showed the highest peak area with 39.09 %, followed by 1,4-benzenedicarboxylic acid, bis (2-ethylhexyl) ester with 13.77 %. These major compounds present in the GCMS analysis are tabulated in **Table 2**. *Cleome amblyocarpa* showed the presence of cleogynol, calycopterin, rhamnocitrin, cleocarpanol, 11-a-acetylbrachy-carpone-22(23)-ene, kaempferol-3,7-dirhamnoside, 1 acetoxycleomblynnol A, and b-sitosterol (El-Ayouty et al., 2024). The compounds present in both *C. amblyocarpa* and CG exhibited the presence of compounds possessing anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antioxidant and antibacterial activities (El-Ayouty et al., 2024). The presence of similar compounds in the different species of *Cleome* have been reported by Khuntia et al., (2022) (Khuntia et al., 2022).

Table 2: Major compounds present in the sample CG

S. No	Compound name	Retention time (minutes)	Peak area	Peak area %
1.	1,4-Benzenedicarboxylic acid, bis(2-ethylhexyl) ester	37.48	195125	13.77
2.	Phenol, 2,4-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl), phosphite (3:1)	38.046	553912	39.09
3.	Phthalic acid, cyclobutyl tridecyl ester	38.308	42714	3.01
4.	4,13-dibenzoyl [2.2] paracyclophane and 1,1,2-triphenylpropene	39.735	110730	7.81
5.	1,1,2-triphenylpropene	39.816	153983	10.87

Figure 2: GCMS analysis of the test sample (CG)

4.3 Docking studies

STAT 1 plays a vital role in signaling the proliferation of interleukins and possesses an effective role in the pathogenesis of different arthritis (Raychaudhuri SK & Raychaudhuri SP, 2017) (Kasperkovitz et al., 2004). Identifying a compound that inhibits its activity will be a potential resource for arthritic management. Towards such approach, phenol, 2,4 -bis (1,1-dimethylethyl)-phosphite (3:1) (PubChem CID: 91601) was docked against signal transducer and activator of transcription 1- alpha/beta (PDB id: 1YVL) (**Table 3**), which showed a binding affinity of -4.7 kcal/mole. This docked complex is considered the first set. Its 2D and 3D interactions are represented in **Figure 3**. Gasteiger charges of phenol, 2,4-bis (1,1 - dimethylethyl)-, phosphite (3:1) merged 63 nonpolar hydrogens and found 18 aromatic carbons. Docked complexes form various bonds with the amino acids of the target proteins at specified distances. The bonds formed with the amino acid and their distance are tabulated in **Table 4**. Hydrogen bonds PHE (B) 1077 and LEU (B) 1078, the hydrophobic alkyl LEU (B) 1078, and hydrophobic pi-alkyl PHE (B) 1077 lies in the slight aromatic edge side. The bonds PHE (B) 1077 and LEU (B) 1078 belong to the H bond donor side. All the hydrogen, pi-donor hydrogen, hydrophobic alkyl and hydrophobic pi-alkyl lies in the interpolated neutral charge. PHE (B) 1077 lies in the hydrophobic region of -1.00 and another pi-donor hydrogen, hydrophobic alkyl and hydrophobic pi-alkyl lies in the hydrophobic region of 3.00. All the hydrogen, pi-donor hydrogen, hydrophobic alkyl and

hydrophobic pi-alkyl lies in between the acidic and basic ionizability region, and SAS region with the value of 25.00. The representation of the interaction between ligand and target protein, showing the bonds is represented in **Figure 4**.

The presence of IL-6 induces the production of proinflammatory cytokines thereby provoking inflammation (Allagui et al., 2023). Thus, inhibiting its production will simultaneously reduce inflammation. Hence, this study aimed to identify the binding potential of CG sample's phytochemical towards the hexameric human IL-6/IL-6 alpha receptor. The second set includes the docking of 1, 4-Benzenedicarboxylic acid/ bis (2-ethyl hexyl) ester (PubChem id: 22932) against the crystal structure of the hexameric human IL-6/IL-6 alpha receptor (PDB id: 1P9M). Gasteiger charges of the ligand merged 38 nonpolar hydrogens and found 6 aromatic carbons. It consisted of 16 rotatable bonds. The docked complex showed a binding affinity of -5.3 kcal/mole (**Table 3**). The bonds formed between the amino acids of proteins and their distance are tabulated in **Table 4**. Both hydrogen bonds lie in-between the aromatic face and edge side, whereas VAL 96 (B) and ASN 144 (B) lie in H-bond donor region. The interpolated charge region of all the hydrogen and hydrophobic bonds lies in the -0.033 to 0.000 region. VAL 96 (B) and ASN 144 (B) lie in the hydrophobic region of -2.00 and ILE 123(B) and LEU 92(B) lie in the hydrophobic region of -3.00. The interaction of ionizability of all bonds lie in-between the acidic and basic regions. Hydrogen bond VAL 96(B) lies in SAS value of 10.00, ASN 144(B) lies in SAS value of 22.5 and hydrophobic pi-alkyl bond PRO 141(B) lies in SAS value of 25.00. The 2D interactions between the ligand and target protein, showing the bonds is represented in **Figure 5**. El-Ayouty et al., (2024), also isolated compounds 1 acetoxycleomblyol A and 11 α -acetylbrachy-carpone-22(23)-ene, from *C. amblyocarpa* and docked it against cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2). 1 acetoxycleomblyol A showed increased effective binding affinity ($-12.60 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) compared to 11 α -acetylbrachy-carpone-22(23)-ene ($-10.44 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) (El-Ayouty et al., 2024). Catethin, a phytochemical of *Cleome arabica* docked against the COX-2 showed better performance than indomethacin, the reference drug (Allagui et al., 2023). This, suggests that the phytoconstituent of *Cleome* possesses effective anti-inflammatory activity. The referenced studies have docked only against the COX-2 protein. The current study remains the first to analyse the docking efficiency of CG's constituent against STAT1 and hexameric human IL-6/IL-6 alpha receptor.

Figure 3: 2D and 3D interactions between ligand and protein of set 1.

Image description: A - 2D interaction of target protein with ligand; B - 3D interaction of target protein with ligand

Figure 4: The position and the bond interactions are shown below.

Image description: A -Aromatic ring of target protein with ligand; B - H-bond donor and acceptor region around target protein and ligand; C - Hydrophobicity region around target protein and ligand; D - Ionizability region around target protein and ligand; E - SAS region around target protein and ligand; F - Interpolated charge region around target protein and ligand.

Figure 5: The 2D interactions between the ligand and target protein (second set), showing the bonds.

Image description: A - 2D interaction of target protein with ligand; B - Aromatic ring of target protein with ligand; C - H-bond donor and acceptor region around target protein and ligand; D - Hydrophobicity region around target protein and ligand; E - Ionizability region around target protein and ligand; F - SAS region around target protein and ligand; G - Interpolated charge region around target protein and ligand.

Table 3: Binding affinities of the docked complexes

Description	Ligand	Target protein	Binding affinity
Docked complex set 1	Phenol, 2,4 –bis (1,1–dimethylethyl)-phosphite (3:1) (PubChem CID: 91601)	Signal transducer and activator of transcription 1-alpha/beta (PDB id: 1YVL)	-4.7 kcal/mole
Docked complex set 2	1, 4-Benzenedicarboxylic acid/ bis (2-ethyl hexyl) ester (PubChem id: 22932)	Hexameric human IL-6/IL-6 alpha receptor (PDB id: 1P9M)	-5.3 kcal/mole

Table 4: Bonds formed between the phytochemicals and the amino acids of their target proteins.

Bonds formed	Amino acid position	Distance (Å)	Bonds formed	Amino acid position	Distance (Å)
Docked complex – First set			Docked complex – Second set		
Hydrogen bond	PHE (B) 1077	3.07	Two conventional hydrogen bonds	VAL 96 (B)	2.19
Pi-donor hydrogen bond	LEU (B) 1078	3.13		ASN 144 (B)	2.27
Two hydrophobic alkyl bonds	LEU (B) 1078	4.74 and 4.89	Hydrophobic alkyl bonds	LEU 92 (B)	5.42
Two hydrophobic pi alkyl bonds	PHE (B) 1077	4.61 and 4.45		ILE 123 (B)	5.01
Hydrophobic alkyl bonds	LEU (B) 1078	4.92	Hydrophobic pi-alkyl bond	PRO 141 (B)	5.32
Hydrophobic pi-pi stacked bond	PHE (B) 1077	3.96			

4.4 MTT assay

MG 63 is a common osteoblast cell line, that is used in multiple studies, especially in antiarthritic studies (Manoharan AL et al., 2023). Thus, the cytotoxicity effects of the CG sample were also studied on MG-63 cell lines, where the effects were in a concentration-dependent manner. This study concludes that CG shows moderate cytotoxicity, and with increased

concentration, it exhibits significant effects. The visualization of cells after treatment with CG (varying concentrations) is represented in **Figure 6**. The concentration required to reduce cell viability by 50% is based on the IC₅₀ value of 483.1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The cell viability % of the control and CG treated samples is graphically represented in **Figure 7**. The higher concentrations of CG showed decreased cell viability, where the lowest viability was observed at 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (56.02%), and approximate complete viability was observed at 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (96.46%). This proves that the CG extract is non-toxic to the cell lines. The chloroform extract of CG leaves also exhibited better anti-cancer activity in adenocarcinoma cells from human colon (HT-29), human hepatocellular liver cell line (HepG2), and lung tumour cells (A549). Its cytotoxicity activity by MTT assay was 23.64 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (IC₅₀) (Ramalingam SivaKumar et al., 2023). Based on the IC₅₀ value, the cells treated showed a notable increase in pro-apoptotic activity. CG treatment increased the apoptosis, without significant necrosis. **Table 5** shows the apoptotic and necrotic indices of the CG extract. Fluorescence microscopy imaging confirmed that treated cells display characteristic chromatin condensation and fragmentation, indicating apoptosis (**Figure 8**).

Figure 6: Comparison of control and CG-treated cells at varying concentrations

Figure 7: Graphical representation of the CG inhibiting cell viability % at different concentrations

Figure 8: Ethidium bromide/acridine orange staining and fluorescence imaging of control and CG treated cells (483.1 µg/ml)

Table 5: Apoptotic and Necrotic indexes of CG extract

S. No	Dead cells	Necrotic cells	Pro-Apoptotic cells	Apoptotic cells	Live cells
1.	0	0	4	0	96
2.	0	0	6	0	94

4.5 Anti-inflammatory assay

Cytokines play a significant role in the pathogenesis of arthritis (Boyle et al., 2015). Especially, targeting the pivotal cytokines such as IL-6 will be more effective. Hence, this study targeted IL-6 with CG extract. ELISA quantifying the IL-6 levels showed distinct variations across the test. Control exhibited 49.44 pg/mL of IL-6. Treatment with LPS showed a significant rise on average of 74.65 pg/mL, indicating a robust inflammatory response. On co-treatment with CG resulted in the reduction of IL-6 on average of 67.62 pg/mL (**Figure 9**). This clearly indicates the potential of CG to combat inflammatory reactions. A similar analysis showed 649.91 pg/ml of IL-6 in the diseased group, which was reduced to 363.50 pg/ml while treating with the ethanolic extract of *Alternanthera bettzickiana* at a dose of 1,000 mg/kg (Manan et al., 2022). Though the study indicates nearly 50% reduction, the concentration needs consideration, where the current study reported effective reduction at 483.1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The fruit extract of *Cleome arabica* showed effective anti-inflammatory properties by reducing IL-6 significantly (Allagui et al., 2023). *Cleome rutidosperma* reduced the IL-6 by LPS mediated anti-inflammatory activity (Ding et al., 2016).

Figure 9: Graphical representation of the IL-6, in various reactions.

4.6 Wound healing assay

Synovial fibroblasts are well known for their initiation in inflammation and destruction of joints, which in turn leads to the progression of arthritis (Dzhambazov B et al., 2023). Therefore, the fibroblast cell lines were used in this study. The cell migration potential of 3T3-L1 fibroblast cells was identified using a wound healing assay. On treating the wound with 130.28 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of CG sample showed reduced wound area, compared to control cells. The initial and cells after 24 hours of incubation is photographically shown in **Figure 10**. This, indicates the enhanced

migratory activity. These results suggest that the CG sample promotes cell migration, highlighting its potential applications in wound healing and tissue repair processes. *Cleome rutidosperma* possesses effective wound healing activity (Ding et al., 2016). The seed of *Cleome viscosa* contained Lupeol (a triterpenoid) that showed maximum wound healing potential (Singh et al., 2017).

Figure 10: Comparison of control and CG treated sample after 0 and 24 hours of incubation.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the leaves of *C. gynandra* showed the presence of multiple therapeutic phytoconstituents through qualitative, quantitative and GCMS analysis. Phenol, 2,4-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-, phosphite (3:1) and 1,4-benzenedicarboxylic acid, bis(2-ethylhexyl) ester showed increased peak areas. These compounds, when docked against STAT1 and hexameric human IL-6/IL-6 alpha receptor (PDB id: 1P9M), showed effective binding affinities of -4.7 kcal/mole and -5.3 kcal/mole, respectively. The hydroalcoholic extract of CG leaves showed effective cytotoxicity (IC₅₀ value = 483.1 µg/mL) in MG-63 cell lines. Likewise, the ELISA test proved the anti-inflammatory effect of CG extract in reducing the IL-6 to 67.62 pg/mL from 74.65 pg/mL (LPS-initiated IL-6). The wound healing assay in 3T3-L1 fibroblast cell lines exhibited reduced wound area, and enhanced cell migration. Hence, this study possibly exhibits the anti-arthritic activity of CG leaves. This study was effectively carried out using hydroalcoholic extract. However, multiple studies have reported the efficacies of chloroform, methanol, and petroleum

ether extracts. Moreover, the other parts of the plant, such as seeds, fruit, and flowers, have also exhibited anti-arthritic properties. Thus, studies using different plant parts and various extracts are warranted in the future. In addition, docking studies can be easily extended towards different phytoconstituents and other target proteins.

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